

CERTIFICATE

OF APRECIATION

SHARQ FALSAFASI

Khayrullayeva Gulmira

THE LEXICAL AND SYNTACTICAL STUDY OF IDIOMS

NOMLI MAQOLASI BILAN ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN TAQDIRLANDI

